

PERCEPTION OF FEMALES ABOUT THE USE OF PAINKILLERS AND HERBAL MEDICATIONS FOR PRIMARY DYSMENORRHEA IN VALACHIL, MANGALORE

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ABSTRACT

Dysmenorrhea is a commonly occurring gynaecological disorder in females that is characterized by painful cramps before or during menstruation. Our study investigates the perception of females regarding use of painkillers and herbal medication in the treatment of primary dysmenorrhea and created awareness using patient information leaflet (PIL). This is a community based interventional study carried out among 109 females of Valachil Mangalore by using pre-validated questionnaires and patient information leaflets for a period of 2.5 months. Results were analyzed using descriptive statistical method [frequency and percentage] and chi-square test. In our study majority of participants 74 (67.88%) were belonging to the age group of 18-25 years. 99(90.82%) of them were previously heard about dysmenorrhea. 73(66.97%) of respondent reported using herbs with fennel being most common 39(35.77%), painkillers were used by 11(10.09%) respondents with mefenamic acid 17(15.59%) and 25(22.93%)

used other mode of medication; most commonly used complementary alternative therapy, 59 was bed rest. 25(22.93%) of respondents believed that CATs(Complementary and Alternative Therapies) were equally effective as analgesic. Chi-Square test showed that the use of medications was not significantly associated with reporting of pain severity and effect on daily life activity. The perception of females regarding the use of herbs was high as compared

to painkiller and other mode of medication. Female believed that CATs were equally effective as painkiller.

KEYWORDS: Dysmenorrhea, Herbs, Painkillers, Complementary and Alternative Therapies, Awareness.

INTRODUCTION

Dysmenorrhea is a common gynaecological condition among females that is characterized by painful cramps before or during menstruation. Menstruation, being a natural phenomenon, often begins between the age of 10 & 16 and has regular impact on a women's life in a various way like mood swings, nausea, vomiting, bloating backpain, leg pain and very commonly pain in lower abdomen.^[1] Primary dysmenorrhea commonly occurs in adolescent girl and younger women. Secondary dysmenorrhea is most commonly seen in women when menstrual pain is accompanied with gynaecological pathologies which include pathological conditions like endometriosis, ovarian, cyst, pelvic inflammatory diseases, myomas or intra uterine devices.^[2,3]

Dysmenorrhea is considered primary when there is no underlying pathology identified. It usually begins within six to twelve months after the commencement of menarche.^[4] Exact mechanism of dysmenorrhea is unclear but most of the study indicates that it usually occurs due to release of unfertilized ovum that cause decrease in progesterone level result in contraction of uterus and shedding of its lining. Decrease in progesterone lead to increase in prostaglandin production that cause increased contraction of uterus thereby restricting the blood flow to uterus thus increasing the sensitivity of pain receptor.^[5]

Many studies have shown that the factors that increase the risk of primary dysmenorrhea includes family history, age, stress, heavy menstrual flow, early age at menarche, irregular cycle, skipping breakfast, smoking, alcohol, anxiety and depression.^[6,7]

Dysmenorrhea also effects the relationship, professional and emotional wellbeing of sufferers. Among college students and school going girls, dysmenorrhea can also lead to absence from school and work in women, in severe cases hospitalization thus effecting productivity and quality of life.^[8,9]

Depending on personal preference and common knowledge, primary dysmenorrhea can be treated in variety of ways. Basically, two approaches are used to treat dysmenorrhea:

pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments. Pharmacological treatment includes use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as ibuprofen, naproxen and mefenamic acid. Other drugs include use of oral contraceptive pills (OCP), anti-spasmodic medication and acetaminophen. NSAIDs relieve the pain instantly by reducing the synthesis of prostaglandin. But there are lots of side effect associated with chronic use which includes GI irritation, salicylism, hypersensitivity, worsening of asthma and peptic ulcer. The adverse effect associated with these drugs have made women to seek non- pharmacological treatments such as heat application, bed rest, yoga, exercise, dietary changes and alternative therapies like acupuncture and massage with no severe adverse effect.^[10]

Medicinal plants or herbs like fennel, ginger, cinnamon and chamomile are used by many doctors worldwide due to their antinociceptive effect. Herbal medication act as a crucial component of healthcare systems worldwide, both traditionally and in modern settings. There are number of herbal remedies for the treatment of dysmenorrhea but because of its slow acting and not instantly relieving pain most of women avoid using herbs even though it has lesser side effects.^[11]

The present study aims at determining the perception of female about the administration of painkillers, herbal and complementary alternative therapies (CATs) in treating dysmenorrhea and educating about primary dysmenorrhea and importance of seeking medical help for improving their quality of life.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Valachil, Mangalore, Karnataka, as a community-based interventional study over a period of 2.5 months. A total of 100 participants were included in the study. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Srinivas Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre, Mukka. The study included females aged between 18 and 45 years. Those suffering from pelvic disorders, pregnant women, females who were not mentally or physically competent, and individuals unwilling to fill out the questionnaire were excluded. Data were collected using structured questionnaires adapted from previous studies and modified to suit the study objectives. The questionnaires were available in both English and Kannada languages and included all relevant variables based on the objectives of the study. The developed questionnaire was validated for appropriateness, clarity, and relevance using the content validity method. During our community visits, we obtained informed consent, explained the purpose of the

study, and administered the questionnaire face to face. Immediately after completing the survey, participants received a patient information leaflet (PIL). All responses and demographic data were recorded and entered into Microsoft Excel for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics Frequencies and percentages were used to summarize participants demographics.

RESULT

In this study, a total of 109 female population were participated. The age group was divided into 3 categories: 18-25 years, 26-35 years and 36- 45 years. Majority of the participant 74 (67.88%) were between the age of 18-25 years, followed by 23 (21.10%) between the age group of 26-35 years and 12 (11%) between the age group of 36-45 years. The Marital status of female population showed that most of the females were single 73 (66.97%) and only 36 (33.02%) were married.

In our study, majority of them 99 (90.82%) had previously heard about primary dysmenorrhea /menstrual cramp, whereas 10 (9.17%) never heard about dysmenorrhea. Most of the women 83 (76.14%) knew that primary dysmenorrhea is painful menstrual cramps whereas, 22 (20.18%) females responded don't know. Majority of the women 49 (44.95%) answered don't know when asked about causes of primary dysmenorrhea and only 41(37.61%) participants responded prostaglandins as its main cause. 45 (41.28%) participants told that they are having family history of PD whereas, 64(58.71%) are not having family history. When asked about risk factors for PD 27(24.77%) participants answered stress, 25(22.93%) of them answered family history, 05(4.58%) of them answered skipping breakfast could be the reason for PD but most of them 39 (35.77%) are unaware about the risk factors for PD. When asked about severity of menstrual cramp, most answered moderate 53 (48.62%), while 29 (26.60%) answered mild and 27 (24.77%) answered severe. Also 54 (49.54%) participants had 5-7 days of menstrual flow, 52(47.70%) having <5 days, 03(2.77%) having the flow >8 days. When asked about regularity of menses in last 1 year, majority had regular menses 101(92.66%) and only 08 (7.33%) had irregular menses. Nature of menstrual flow is moderate in 83 (76.14%) participants, 15 (13.76%) of them reported heavy flow, 11 (10.09%) reported light menstrual flow. Also 80 (73.39%) of them feel abdominal pain during menstrual flow, 29 (26.60%) of them feel abdominal pain before bleeding and no participants reported abdominal pain after bleeding stopped. 89 (81.65%) females suffer from pain for the period of <3 days, 14 (12.84%) reported for 3-5 days, 6

(5.50%) reported for >5 days. Pain affects daily life activities in 68 (62.28%) of respondents and does not affect the daily life activity in 41 (37.61%) of respondents, which often disturbing household chores 37 (33.94%), attendance of lecture 15 (13.76%), concentration at lecture 09 (8.25%), disturb sleep 26 (23.85%) and none 22 (20.18%). Although only 16 (14.67%) of participants reported hospital visits during pain and 93(85.32%) of participants never visited hospital during pain. A significant proportion of participants 87 (79.81%) experienced mood swings/cravings, whereas 22 (20.18%) of participant does not experienced mood swings/cravings. Common sources that triggers menstrual cramps included spicy food 45 (41.28%), chocolate 13(11.92%), caffiene 08 (7.33%) and none 44 (39.44%). In terms of management of pain, most of the participants preferred herbs 73 (66.97%) over painkillers 11(10.09%) and others 25(22.93%), while alternative therapies such as bed rest 59(54.12%) and the use of a heating pad 21(19.26%), massage 06 (5.50%) were common and 23(21.10%) of participants preferred no alternative therapies. Also 85 (77.98%) of the respondents did not used any medication for menstrual pain, while 17 (15.59%) participants were using mefanamic acid, 04 (3.66%) were using ibuprofen, 02 (1.83%) were using paracetamol and 01 (0.91%) were using diclofenac. Side effects from medication were relatively uncommon 96 (88.07%), with only 13 (11.92%) respondents were reporting with side effects. Majority of the participants 81 (74.31%) have reported that they don't know about the common side effects occur after taking the medication, while 18 (16.51%) of them have been reported with gastric irritation, 1 (0.91%) have been reported with ulcer and 09 (8.25%) respondent reported with both gastric irritation and ulcer.

Among the herbal medications, fennel 39 (35.77%) was most commonly preferred by the participants over fenugreek 27 (24.77%), corriander 21 (19.26%), while 22(20.18%) participants did not use any of herbal medications. Complementary therapies were viewed as equally effective than analgesic by 25 (22.93%) of participants and less effective 15 (13.76%), more effective 23 (21.10%) and majority 46 (42.20%). Overall, a large majority 91 (83.49%) of participant expressed interest in receiving more information about primary dysmenorrhea while 18 (16.51%) participants were not interested in receiving more information about primary dysmenorrhea.

The table below summarize the association between severity of pain, its impact on daily life activity and the medication used by the respondents. Out of 73 participants using herbs, majority experienced moderate level of pain (35), followed by mild pain (21) and severe pain

(17) with most of participants (45) responded that pain affect daily life activity, (28) participants responded that it does not affect the daily life activity. Out of 11 participants using painkillers, 2 participants experienced mild level of pain, followed by moderate pain (5), and severe pain (4) of which 9 reported that pain affect daily life activity and 2 reported that it does not affect daily life activity. Out of 25 participants who relied on other method of treatment, 13 participants experienced moderate pain, followed by 6 experienced mild and 6 experienced severe pain while 14 participants reported that pain affect daily life activity and 11 participants reported that it does not affect daily life activity. The association between medication with pain severity and daily life activity was not statistically significant in our study. Hence null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 1: Comparing the link between pain severity and daily life activities in relation to primary dysmenorrhea.

Pain severity	Medication				Percentage (%)
	Herbs	Painkiller	Other	Grand Total	
Mild	21	2	6	29	26.60
Moderate	35	5	13	53	48.62
Severe	17	4	6	27	24.77
Grand Total	73	11	25	109	
Chi- square = 1.42 p value = 0.997698 p < 0.05* Since the p value is >0.05, we can conclude that there is no statistically significant association between pain severity and medications used for primary dysmenorrhea.					
Pain affecting daily life activity	Medication				Percentage (%)
	Herbs	Painkillers	Others	Grand Total	
Yes	45	9	14	68	62.38
No	28	2	11	41	37.61
Grand Total	73	11	25	109	
Chi – square = 2.2217 p value = 0.898222 p<0.05* Since the p value is > 0.05, we can conclude that there is no statistically significant association between pain affecting daily life activity and medication used.					

DISCUSSION

Primary dysmenorrhea is common gynaecological condition among the females. This community-based study was conducted on general female population of aged 18-45 years of Valachil Mangalore to assess the perception of females about the use of painkillers and herbal medication for primary dysmenorrhea.

The aim of this study was to assess the perception of female about the use of painkillers and herbal medication, to assess the link between pain severity and daily life activities, to

evaluate the awareness and impact of medication and to give awareness using patient information leaflets (PIL) about primary dysmenorrhea. Validation of questionnaires was done, and it was in both English and Kannada languages.

The current study was conducted among 109 female participants. The participants were categorized into 3 age groups; Most of them were under the age group of 18-25 years and counting 74 (67.88%), 23 (21.10%) participants were belonging to 26-35 years and 12 (11.00%) participants belonging to 36-45 years of age group.

Most of the female population 99 (90.82%) were heard about primary dysmenorrhea with 10 (9.17%) never heard about primary dysmenorrhea. The present study was found that common risk factors of PD were stress 27(24.77%), family history 25(22.93%), Early age of menarche 13(11.92%) and 39(35.77%) were not know about risk factor of PD. Most of the females doesn't have the family history of PD 64 (58.71%) and 45 (41.28%) having the family history of PD, which showed inconsistent with a previously conducted study in Saudi Arabia by Ali A *et al*^[2] where 60.7% of the participants having family history of dysmenorrhea.

According to our study, shows that severity of menstrual cramp was moderate in the population of 53 (48.62%) females, mild in 29 (26.60%) and severe in 27 (24.77%) females, 54 (49.54%) having duration of menstrual flow of 5-7 days, 52(47.70%) having <5 and 03 (2.77%) having menstrual flow >8. These above reports are similar to the previous research study conducted by Tahir A *et al.*^[1] 101(92.66%) female had regular menses in last 1 year and 08(7.33%) of females had irregular menses this result shows similar with Tahir A *et al*^[1], Ali A *et al*^[2], Abubakar U *et al*^[5] and Bakhsh H *et al.*^[7] Nature of menstrual flow is moderate in 83 (76.14%) participants, 15 (13.76%) of them reported heavy flow and 11 (10.09%) are reported light flow. These responses were similar with Ameade EPK *et al.*^[3]

The survey results revealed that the majority 83 (76.14%) of respondents sometimes experienced other menstrual symptoms and 26 (23.85%) always experienced other menstrual symptoms, with back pain 65 (59.63%) being the most common and other symptoms like vomiting 12 (11.00%), diarrhoea 06 (5.50%). Pain affects daily life activities in 68 (62.28%) of respondents and does not affect the daily life activity in 41(37.61%) of respondents, these above results showed inconsistent with a previously conducted study in Northern Ghana by Ameade EPK *et al.*^[3] A significant proportion of participant 87 (79.81%) experienced mood swings/cravings and 22 (20.18%) participants does not experienced mood swings/cravings,

which showed inconsistent with a previously conducted study in Saudi Arabia by Ali A *et al.*^[2] Common sources that trigger menstrual cramps included spicy food 45 (41.28%), chocolate 13(11.92%), caffeine 08 (7.33%) and none 43 (39.44%) this finding is not similar with previously conducted study by Wang YL *et al.*^[6]

In terms of management of pain, most of the participants preferred herbs 73 (66.97%) over painkillers 11 (10.09%) and others 25 (22.93%), while alternative therapies such as bed rest 59 (54.12%) and the use of a heating pad 21 (19.26%), massage 06 (5.50%) were common and 23 (21.10%) of participants preferred no alternative therapies. This finding was inconsistent with previously conducted study by Zaman A Y *et al.*^[4], where 51.9% were using medications. 85 (77.98%) of the respondents did not used any medication for menstrual pain while 17 (15.59%) participants were using mefenamic acid, 04 (3.66%) were using ibuprofen, 02 (1.83%) were using paracetamol and 01 (0.91%) were using diclofenac. This result was not compatible with the study conducted by Ali A *et al.*^[2] Side effects from medication were relatively uncommon 96 (88.07%), with only 13 (11.92%) respondents were reporting side effects. Majority of the participants 81 (74.31%) have reported that they don't know about the common side effects occur after taking the medication while 18 (16.51%) of them have been reported with stomach upset, 1(0.91%) have been reported with mouth ulcer and 09(8.25%) respondent reported with both stomach upset and mouth ulcer this result shows inconsistent with Tahir A *et al.*^[1]

Among the herbal medications, fennel 39 (35.77%) was most commonly preferred by the participants over fenugreek 27 (24.77%), coriander 21(19.26%) and 22 (20.18%) did not use any of herbal medications. Complementary therapies were viewed as equally effective than analgesic by 25 (22.93%) of participants and less effective 15 (13.76%), more effective 23 (21.10%) and 46 (42.20%) 0 reported don't know. The effectiveness of the CAT have been confirmed in previous study conducted by Abubakar U *et al.*^[5] Overall, a large majority 91(83.49%) of participants expressed interest in receiving more information about primary dysmenorrhea while 18(16.51%) participants were not interested in receiving more information about primary dysmenorrhea.

In the present study Chi- square test showed that degree of pain and use of medication was not significantly associated ($p>0.05$). This result was inconsistent with previous study conducted by Zaman A Y *et al.*^[4] This study also found that there was no statistical

significance association between medication used and pain affecting daily life activity, this finding was consistent with the previously conducted study by Zaman A Y *et al.*^[4]

CONCLUSION

Dysmenorrhea is common gynecological conditions affecting the quality of life of females. Primary dysmenorrhea (PD) is a public health problem affecting different parts of women's life, and if left untreated, it may lead to complications. Our study revealed that unmarried females, especially those in the 18- 25 years of age group were more affected by PD.

The current study showed that more than half of the participants opted for herbs to relieve pain rather than painkillers. This shows reliance on traditional and alternative remedies like fennel, fenugreek, and coriander.

The study found that association between medication with pain severity and daily life activity was not statistically significant. Hence, we accept null hypothesis. This implies that even the use of medication was not fully effective in minimizing the disturbance caused by PD.

Education and awareness were provided by using PIL about primary dysmenorrhea and medication used for it. This information helps to empower women to manage their menstrual health effectively and to seek appropriate care.

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